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Review Article

Niosomes: A Review Of Drug Delivery System

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ABSTRACT

In the past few years, there has been a significant change in the way infectious disease management and vaccination practices are carried out. With the development of biotechnology and genetic engineering, numerous biologicals targeted at certain diseases have been developed; additionally, the efficient distribution of these biologicals has received attention. Comparatively speaking, niosomes are less expensive, more stable, nontoxic, and biodegradable than liposomes because they are made of non-ionic surfactants. However, they are more stable than liposomes during the production and storage processes. This paper examines the recent surge in interest in niosomes across several scientific fields, with a focus on medical applications. A thorough overview of niosome types, characterization, applications, and preparation methods is also given in this article.

INTRODUCTION

By increasing the concentration of the medication in the target tissues while decreasing the relative concentration of the drug in non-target tissues, targeted drug delivery seeks to achieve these goals. As a result, the medication concentrates in the desired location. As a result, the medicine doesn't affect the tissues around it. As a result, localization

guarantees that the treatment functions as efficiently as feasible and prevents drug loss. Drugs have been targeted using a variety of carriers, such as erythrocytes, niosomes, liposomes, microspheres, serum proteins, and immunoglobulin. [1,11] In vivo, niosomes function similarly to liposomes, prolonging the drug's circulation while altering its distribution

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throughout the body and stability during metabolism. [1,13] As with liposomes, the properties of niosomes are determined by the type of bilayer and the method of synthesis. Reportedly, the intercalation of cholesterol lowers the amount of entrapment during formulation and, as a result, the entrapment's effectiveness.[1,14] Niosomes have been used to study the nature of the immunological response elicited by antigens. [1,15] While niosomal drug delivery technology is still in its early stages of development, it has demonstrated potential as a leishmaniasis treatment and as a cancer chemotherapy agent. [1] Niosomes, which have a bilayer structure and are created when cholesterol and non-ionic surfactants self-associate in an aqueous phase, are among the most promising drug carriers. Niosomes are biocompatible, biodegradable, and non-immunogenic. They have a very stable, long shelf life, and allow for regulated and/or continuous drug delivery to the target site. [2,12]

ADVANTAGES OF NIOSOME

1. Niosomes improve oral bioavailability by delivering a controlled release of medication.
2. They can improve the stability of the medication that is entrapped by ensnaring hydrophilic, lipophilic, and amphiphilic pharmaceuticals.
3. The therapeutic efficacy of the drug entrapped inside niosomes can be enhanced by confining its effects to target cells and shielding it from its biological surroundings, which lowers the drug's clearance.
4. The niosomal dispersion in an aqueous phase can be emulsified in the latter phase in order to regulate the drug's release rate and supply normal vesicles in an outer non-aqueous phase.
5. The capacity to encapsulate medications and restrict their release to decrease the body's removal of these compounds and reduce systemic toxicity.

6. Due to their adaptability, these can be easily modified to suit requirements. They are stable and osmotically active.
7. They may improve the rate at which medications pierce the skin.
8. There are other ways to administer them, such as topically, parenterally, orally.
9. Because niosomes include non-ionic surfactants, they are biodegradable, biocompatible, and non-immunogenic.
10. Surfactants don't require special handling or storage techniques.[3]

DISADVANTAGES OF NIOSOMES

1. The physical instability resulting from drug fusion, aggregation, and leakage.
2. Opulent.
3. Require certain storage conditions.
4. The level of purity in natural phospholipids varies.
5. The shelf life of the dispersion is decreased by drug encapsulation hydrolysis. [3]

STRUCTURE OF NIOSOME

The spherical niosomes are made up of a variety of microscopic lamellar (unilamellar or multilamellar) components (Figure 1). The bilayer is created by combining nonionic surfactants—with or without cholesterol—with a charge inducer. [4, 8, 16]

NIOSOME COMPOSITIONS: [18]

There are two principal ingredients needed to prepare niosomes:

1. Cholesterol
2. Non-ionic surfactants

1. Cholesterol:

Cholesterol is a derived steroid that is used to give produced niosomes their proper stiffness, shape, and conformation. [6]

2. Nonionic surfactants:

The following non-ionic surfactants are commonly used in niosome manufacturing. 60, 40, 20, 85, and 80 spans, for example 20–40–60–80-year-old tweens (30, 35, 52, 58, 72, and 76) Brijns An

hydrophile the hydrophobic head and tail of non-ionic surfactants are among their properties.[6]

Fig no 1: Structure of niosome

TYPES OF NIOSOME :

The different types of niosomes are as follows:

a. Multi lamellar vesicles (MLV),

b. Large unilamellar vesicles (LUV),

c. Small unilamellar vesicles (SUV).[5]

Table no 1: Different types of Niosome

Parameter	Multi lamellar vesicles (MLV)	Large unilamellar vesicles (LUV)	Small unilamellar vesicles (SUV)
Vesicle Size	Greater than 0.05 μm	0.025-0.05 μm	Greater than 0.10 μm
Method of Preparation	Hand shaking Method	Sonication Extrusion Method Solvent Dilution Technique	Reverse Phase evaporation Method

METHODS OF PREPARATION OF NIOSOMES

1. Ether injection method

The ether injection method basically entails slowly injecting warm water maintained at 60°C with a surfactant solution dissolved in diethyl ether. A 14-gauge needle is used to introduce the surfactant mixture in ether into the material's aqueous solution. Ether vapourization produces single-layer vesicles. The niosomes produced range in diameter from 50 to 1000 nm depending on the parameters used. [6]

2. Hand shaking method (thin film hydration technique): [18]

In this procedure, the cholesterol and surfactant are dissolved in a round-bottomed flask using a

volatile organic solvent (such as diethylether, chloroform, or methanol). A rotary evaporator is used to extract the organic solvent at room temperature (20°C), leaving behind a thin coating of solid mixture that is deposited on the flask wall. Rehydrating the dried surfactant film with aqueous phase at 0 to 60 °C while gently stirring can result in the formation of multilamellar niosomes. [6]

3. Sonication method :

In this procedure, a 10-ml glass vial holding the surfactant/cholesterol mixture is filled with an aliquot of the drug solution in buffer. Using a titanium probe, niosomes are created by sonicating the liquid for three minutes at 60 °C. [6]

4. Micro fluidization method : [21]

Micro fluidization is a more modern technique for producing unilamellar vesicles with a certain size distribution. This method is based on the submerged jet theory, which describes how two fluidized streams collide at very high speeds inside carefully designed microchannels inside an interaction chamber. The energy delivered to the system remains in the region where niosomes form because the thin liquid sheet impingement is positioned along a single front. The result is the synthesis of more compact, reliable, and repeatable niosomes.[6]

5. Multiple membrane extrusion method :

A thin film is formed when a mixture of diacetyl phosphate, cholesterol, and surfactant in chloroform evaporates. Aqueous drug polycarbonate membranes are used to hydrate the film. Through up to eight passages, the solution is extruded via these membranes. and the final result is the suspension that follows. It's a practical way to manage loud size. [6]

6. Reverse Phase Evaporation Technique :[20]

In this process, the cholesterol and surfactant are dissolved in a 1:1 ether and chloroform solution. This is combined with an aqueous phase that contains medicine, and the two stages are sonicated concurrently at 4-5°C. PBS, or phosphate buffered saline, is added once a clear gel has formed. which receives more sonication. The organic phase is removed at 40 °C using low pressure. The resultant viscous niosome suspension is heated on a water bath at 60°C for 10 minutes, and then it is diluted with PBS to form niosomes. [6]

7. Transmembrane pH gradient (inside acidic) Drug Uptake Process:

A solution of surfactant and cholesterol is dissolved using chloroform. Next, as the solvent evaporates at a lower pressure, a thin layer forms on the wall of the flask with a circular bottom. This film is hydrated with 300mm citric acid (PH 4.00)

via vertex mixing. Next, three rounds of sharing, freezing, and sonication are applied to the resultant multilamellar vesicles. This niosomal suspension is mixed with an aqueous solution containing 10 mg/ml of the drug, and vortexes are formed. Next, 1M disodium phosphate is added to the sample to raise its pH to 7.0–7.2. This mixture is heated to 60 °C for 10 minutes in order to form niosomes. [6]

8. The Bubble Method : [21]

A three-necked flask with a spherical bottom that is submerged in water to control temperature is the bubbling unit. The third neck receives nitrogen supplies, while the first and second necks have a thermometer and a reflux that is cooled by water. Both cholesterol and surfactant are distributed concurrently in this buffer (PH 7.4). The dispersion is then quickly 'bubbled' at the same temperature with nitrogen gas to create niosomes after being blended for 15 seconds with a high shear homogenizer.[6,23]

FACTORS AFFECTING NIOSOMES FORMULATION:

1. Drug:

The drug's interaction with surfactant head groups raises the charge and mutual repulsion of the surfactant bilayers within niosomes, hence increasing the vesicle's size. Drugs are trapped in the lengthy PEG chains of polyoxymethylene glycol (PEG) coated vesicles, which inhibits their capacity to swell. The degree of entrapment is influenced by the medication's hydrophilic lipophilic equilibrium. [7]

2. Amount and type of surfactant:

Because the surface free energy of HLB surfactants, such as Span 85 (HLB 1.8) to Span 20 (HLB 8.6), drops as the surfactant's hydrophobicity increases, the mean size of niosomes grows proportionately. The vesicles' bilayers can exist in either a liquid or gel state, contingent on many factors such as temperature, surfactant type, and the inclusion of other

components like cholesterol. Alkyl chains are present in the gel state in a well-organized form, while the bilayer structure is more disorganised in the liquid state. The temperature at which the gel liquid phase change occurs describes the lipids and surfactants. The phase transition temperature of the surfactant influences entrapment efficiency, span 60 has a greater.

3. Cholesterol content and charge:

The hydrodynamic diameter and niosome trapping efficiency were enhanced by cholesterol. Cholesterol generally has two effects: it increases the chain order of liquid state bilayers while also making the chain orders of gel state bilayers more disordered. At high concentrations of cholesterol, the gel state gives way to a liquid-ordered phase. The resultant bilayers were stiffer due to a delayed rate of encapsulated material release caused by a higher cholesterol content in the bilayers. Charge has the tendency to increase the overall entrapped volume in multilamellar vesicle formations by lengthening the interlamellar distance between consecutive bilayers. [7]

4. Methods of Preparation :

The vesicles produced by the hand shaking approach have a diameter of 0.35–13 nm, which is larger than that of the ether injection method. One technique for producing tiny niosomes is reverse phase evaporation. The micro fluidization process yields more uniformity and smaller vesicles. Drug entrapment and retention were improved in niosomes produced by the trans membrane pH gradient, an acidic drug absorption method. [8, 22]

5. Resistance To Osmotic Stress:

When niosomes are suspended in a hypertonic salt solution, their diameter decreases. After a first slow release with slight vesicle enlargement in a hypotonic salt solution, a faster release could result from mechanically loosening the vesicles' structure under osmotic stress. [8,23,15]

EVALUATIONS OF NOISOME:

1. Scanning electron microscopy

One crucial feature of niosomes is their particle size. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to examine the size distribution of niosomes as well as their surface appearance (roundness, smoothness, and aggregate formation). Using double-sided tape, niosomes were sprayed onto aluminium stubs. The aluminium stub was inserted into the scanning electron microscope's vacuum chamber (XL 30 ESEM with EDAX, Philips, Netherlands). The samples were examined using a Gaseous Secondary Electron Detector XL 30 (0.8 torr working pressure, 30.00 KV acceleration voltage) to determine their morphology (Philips, Netherlands).[6,24]

2. Vesicle size measurement

In the same medium that was used to produce them, the vesicle dispersions were diluted around 100 times. A particle size analyser (Laser diffraction particle size analyser, Sympatec, Germany) was used to measure the vesicles' size. The setup consists of a multielement detector that concentrates a point-focused He-Ne laser beam with a minimum power of 5 mW at 632.8 nm using a Fourier lens [R-5] and a small volume sample holding cell (Su cell). The material was mixed using a stirrer before the vesicle size was determined. Hu C. and Rhodes 7 state that the average particle size of niosomes generated from niosomes is about 6 µm, as opposed to 14 µm for ordinary niosomes[6,24]

3. Entrapment efficiency

By completely disrupting the vesicles with 50% n-propanol or 0.1% Triton X-100 and evaluating the resultant solution using the suitable assay method for the drug, it is possible to assess how much drug is still contained in niosomes. As previously mentioned, gel filtration or dialysis centrifugation can be used to remove the untrapped medication. [6,24]

4. Stability studies

The optimised batch was kept in hermetically sealed vials at various temperatures to gauge the

niosomes' stability. The surface characteristics and percentage of drug maintained in niosomes and niosomes produced from pro niosomes were chosen as metrics for evaluation of the stability since instability of the formulation would reflect in drug leakage and a deterioration. on the rate of medication retention. At intervals of 0, 1, 2, and 3 months, samples of the niosomes were taken, and they were examined for colour changes and surface characteristics. The amount of medication that remained after the niosomes were hydrated was calculated, and the niosomes were analysed using the proper analytical techniques (UV spectroscopy, HPLC methods, etc.).[6,11]

5. Zeta potential analysis

Zeta potential analysis is utilised to determine the colloidal properties of the produced formulations. A zeta potential analyser (Zeta plus TM, Brookhaven Instrument Corporation, New York, USA) based on electrophoretic light scattering and laser Doppler velocimetry approach was used to detect the properly diluted niosomes created from pro niosome dispersion. A temperature of 25 °C was established. Direct measurements were made of the charge on the vesicles and their mean zeta potential values with standard deviation.[6,25]

APPLICATIONS OF NIOSOMES:

1. Targeting of bioactive agents

- a. The vesicles are more often inside the RES cells. Opsonins, circulating serum components that recognise them for elimination, are what cause it. On the other hand, liver parasite infection and animal tumours that are known to spread to the spleen and liver have both been treated with this localised drug accumulation. [16,9]
- b. To organs other than reticulo-endothelial system(RES) :[16,17]

Antibodies enable targeting of specific body regions by the carrier system. Immunoglobulins are a useful tool for drug carrier targeting since they seem to have an affinity for the lipid surface.

Many cells have the intrinsic ability to recognise and bind particular carbohydrate determinants, and this property can be used to target the transport system to particular cells. [9, 26, 27]

2.Delivery of peptide drugs

Peptide stability was reported to increase significantly¹⁸ with niosomal entrapment oral delivery of 9-desglycinamide, 8-arginine vasopressin in an in vitro intestinal loop model. In order to gain a better understanding of the nature of the immune response to antigens, niosomes have been used in immunological studies. Niosomes are said to be an efficient adjuvant due to their immunological specificity, low toxicity, and long half-life. [15, 9]

3. Niosome as a carrier for Haemoglobin

Because niosomal suspension has a visible spectrum that may be superimposed on top of that of free haemoglobin, it can be used as a carrier for haemoglobin. Furthermore, permeable to oxygen, vesicles have the ability to modify the haemoglobin dissociation curve in a way that is similar to non-encapsulated haemoglobin. [9, 28]

4. Ophthalmic drug delivery

In the meantime, the efficacy of a topical gel made of elastic niosome particles loaded with papain has been compared to that of conventional nanomaterials. In comparison to traditional nanomaterials, elastic produced niosome particles showed increased papain penetration, less scarring, and improved transdermal absorption. Elastic-fabricated niosome particles enhanced the cutaneous penetration and chemical stability of gallic acid, suggesting that they could be good carriers for skin-anti-aging agents. [30] Similar to this, the film hydration method was utilised to successfully encapsulate black tea extract, which is frequently used as an antioxidant for the skin. The gallic acid and caffeine in the tea leaf extract were successfully released from niosomal particles and penetrated the dermis, according to in vitro penetration studies. [31]

5. Niosomes for the Delivery of Anti-Scarring Ingredients

An in vivo comparative study was conducted to gauge the pace of penetration into a rabbit's skin when papain gel was produced as elastic niosomes and nanospheres for the treatment of skin scars. The elastic niosomes containing papain were produced by sonication and the thin film hydration technique. Non-ionic surfactant (tween 61), cholesterol (a bilayer inducing agent), sodium cholate (an edge activator), and a solvent mixture of chloroform and methanol were the components used in the fabrication process. When compared to other forms of the same medication, such as non-elastic niosomes and nanospheres, the papain elastic niosomes showed better amounts and fluxes of accumulation over a three-month period. Histological investigations revealed that the elastic papain niosomes significantly reduced the height of the treated scars as well as the quantity of collagen fibres. [10, 32]

CONCLUSION

Recent advancements in scientific study have endorsed small molecules, such as proteins and vaccines, as a key class of medical medicines. They do, however, come with a host of drug-related challenges, including as limited bioavailability, suitable drug administration techniques, physical and chemical instability, and potentially harmful side effects. The utility of niosomes for the delivery of proteins and biologicals is questionable, particularly with regard to the encapsulation of potentially harmful drugs including anti-AIDS, anti-cancer, and anti-viral drugs. It provides a workable carrier system as opposed to ionic drug carriers, which are typically detrimental and inappropriate. On the other hand, niosome technology is still developing. Because it is a promising method of delivering customised drugs, research is being done to develop a technology suitable for mass production.

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